

CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS BHAT-BHATENI SUPERMARKET

BY

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*A Project Work Report submitted to Pokhara University in partial fulfillment of the
requirements for the degree of*

Bachelor of Business Administration

at the

Medhavi College

Pokhara University

Shankhamul, Kathmandu

September, 2019

Declaration

I hereby declare that the project work report entitled “Customer Satisfaction towards Bhat-Bhateni Supermarket” submitted for the BBA is my original work and the Project Work Report has not formed the basis for award of any degree, diploma, or other similar titles.

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Subekchha Bhattarai

Date:

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Project Work titled “**Customer Satisfaction towards Bhat-Bhateni Supermarket**” by **Subekhha Bhattarai (17030202)** for the partial fulfillment of the requirements of BBA embodies the bonafide work done by him/her under my supervision.

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Acknowledgement:

The study entitled “**Customer Satisfaction towards Bhat-Bhateni Supermarket**” has been conducted to satisfy the partial requirement for the degree of Bachelors of Business Administration (BBA) of Pokhara University.

The success and final outcome of this report required a lot of guidance and assistance from many people. I am extremely fortunate to have got this all along, the completion of my project report with the supervision of **Mr. Chetan Acharya**.

I would like to extend my thanks to Pokhara University and Medhavi College for giving me an opportunity to do the report on the topic “Customer Satisfaction towards Bhat-Bhateni Supermarket” and providing for all support and guidance which helped to complete the project on time.

I am extremely grateful to all the respondents who participated in the research and provide me the required information based on which the project report is based upon. I would also thank for providing time to fill up the questionnaire despite their busy schedule.

Lastly, I would also like to thank all my classmates and friends who helped me during research and while preparing the report in various way. I would also like to thank them for all the encouragement and their constant motivation.

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Subekchha Bhattarai

September, 2019

Abstract:

This project work report is about Customer Satisfaction towards Bhat-Bhateni Supermarket. It has shown vast growth in economic conditions and branches are adding day by day. Some issues and problems were addressed through questionnaires and to some extent it helped to fulfill its objectives and research questions. This research was carried out by keeping in mind the Significance/Rationale of the study

The variables were price of products, quality of products, location of supermarket, variety of products, service of staffs and loyalty of customers. This research used mix research approach (qualitative and quantitative). Causal comparative research design and descriptive research design were used.

105 samples were taken. Random and Convenience were carried out to find the result. Primary data were only used and those were collected via structured questionnaire (descriptive, yes/no, multiple choice and likert) were used. Mean, Standard Deviation, Correlation and Regression were found for this research.

In order to examine the validity & reliability of Likert scale questionnaire, Cronbach Alpha test was used. It was found that variety of products and service of staffs did not have significant relationship with customer satisfaction. But also variables have positive and significant relationship with customer satisfaction.

Abbreviation

BBSM	Bhat-Bhateni Supermarket
i.e.	that is
BBA	Bachelor in Business Administration
CSR	Corporate Social Responsibility
CSD	Customer Service Desk
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
ANOVA	Analysis of Variance
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Science
SLC	School Leaving Certificate
SEE	Secondary School of Examination

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CHAPTER I: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background of study:

Philip Kotler defines customer satisfaction as a 'person's feeling of pleasure or disappointment which resulted from comparing a product's perceived performance or outcome against his/her expectations'.

By definition of Supermarket “A larger store that sells a variety of food and households items to Consumers”.

According to Sexana (2002), customer satisfaction is a function of customer’s expectation from the firm.

Oliver (1997) defined satisfaction as the customer’s fulfillment response. It is a judgment that a product or service feature, or the product or service itself, provided a pleasurable level of consumption related fulfillment.

Howard & Sheth (1969) defined satisfaction as the buyer’s cognitive state of being adequately or inadequately rewarded for the scarifies he has undergone.

Beard, Client Heartbeat Blog. (2014) have pointed out the importance of consumer satisfaction as: It helps to minimize negative word of mouth. It’s comparatively cheaper to retain consumers than attract new one. It helps to increase consumer life time value. It’s the main point of differentiation. It’s the main indicator to determine the consumer repurchase intention and loyalty.

Kai, Hans & Ostergaard (2001) found customer satisfaction and loyalty are becoming increasingly important factors in modern retailing a market characterized by slow growth and intense competition. Also, European retailing was changing rapidly; developers were concentrating on increase in store and ownership.

Walter & Paul (1970), consumer behavior is the process whereby individual decide whether, what, how and from when to purchase goods and services.

Retailer Western Fruit Jobber (1917), the concept of a self-service grocery store was developed by American entrepreneur Clarence Saunders and his Piggy Wiggly stores opened in Memphis, Tennessee, in 1916. Saunders was awarded a number of patents for the

ideas he incorporates into the stores. The stores were a financial success began to offer franchises. In 1990, a rapid transformation of the malls and Supermarkets evolved in developing countries. Transformation concentrated to major areas such as: Latin America, South-East Asia, China and South Africa.

Polat & Kulter,(2007),determined that the factors related to product diversity, product quality, inner atmosphere and appearance, quick shopping facility the attitudes and interest of the staff, and the prices were found to be important consideration in customer preference for supermarket.

One of the researcher scholars of Swami Ramanand Teerth Marathwada University, Rana , (2013), suggested that consumer satisfaction study would help businessmen, government policy makers and corporate for future references as it helps to understand consumer services provided by shopping malls.

According to history of Bhat- Bhateni (2017), Mr. and Mrs. Min Bdr Gurung started Bhat-Bhateni cold store in 1984.since 1984 Bhat- Bhateni has grown from 120 sq feet store to become Nepal's no 1 retail store tax payer with more than 100000 customers daily. It continues to be a leader in corporate social responsibility (CSR) and employment opportunity to become key driver for company's success.

Many factors contribute to retailer's overall performance. Literature indicates that retail performance should be judged on multiple dimensions based on customer perception, operational efficiency and financial performance. (Stem &Gregory, 2004; Michael & Barton, 2004).

1.2 Statement of Problem:

Customer satisfaction enables us to know about buying decision of customers and possible sectors that might need an improvement. In olden days provisional stores were used in retails for purchasing products in daily basis. Due to busy schedules, in city and nearby areas the concept of supermarket is increasing. We all know that variety of products are found under one roof, so supermarkets popularity is increasing day by day. In comparison to global market our nation has fewer supermarkets.

However, pressure related to supermarkets undergoes some issues. Some criticisms and complaints regarding services, cost, variety, loyalty, location etc are there. According to

customer's viewpoint, bad experiences, limited to urban areas, lack of discount, unmanaged management and rudeness of staffs etc caused problem towards supermarkets. Cost of product is also high which limit shopping markets to high income based classes. Normal income is not usually focused. Also due to mismanagement customer's complaint of having expired goods as products are stored in bulk. In case of variety and brand of products they promise to provide better but these supermarkets products are Chinese which are quite not reliable. Customers do buy products but grocery items are rather sold than other products.

1.3 Objective of Study:

- (i) To analysis the customer satisfaction towards Bhat- Bhateni supermarket.
- (ii) To examine price, quality of product and services, location of supermarket etc.
- (iii) To get information regarding issues and problems via customers in Bhat-Bhateni supermarket.

1.4 Research Questions and Hypothesis:

1.4.1 Research questions:

- (i) What are the factors which influences the customer satisfaction towards BBSM?
- (ii) How does price of any product influences the customer satisfaction?
- (iii) What is the relationship between location of supermarket and customer's satisfaction?
- (iv) Why quality of product influences the customer satisfaction?
- (v) What varieties of products are found in BBSM?
- (vi) What sorts of services are provided by Bhat-Bhateni staffs?
- (vii) How does loyalty of customers influence the BBSM?

1.4.2 Hypothesis:

There are basically two types of hypothesis. Null & Alternative.

Null hypothesis: It is a proposition that states an exact relationship between two variables. It is denoted by H_0 .

Alternate hypothesis: It is a statement expressing a relationship between two variables or no difference between two groups. It is denoted by H_1 .

- (i) H_1 : There is a significant relationship between price of products and customer satisfaction.
- (ii) H_2 : There is a significant relationship between quality of products and customer satisfaction.
- (iii) H_3 :There is a significant relationship between location of supermarket and customer satisfaction.
- (iv) H_4 : There is a significant relationship between variety of products and customer satisfaction.
- (v) H_5 : There is a significant relationship between service provided by staffs and customer satisfaction.
- (vi) H_6 : There is a significant relationship between loyalty of customers and customer satisfaction.

1.5 Significant/Rationale of the study:

People's preference is changing day by day. With the growing of busy life supermarkets are built with concept of getting products under one roof.

Retail scenario is presently facing similar situation as the "mom and pop" stores in developing nations faced in the emergence of big box retailers. The new expansion of retail formats are adaptation of western formats fetching moderate to lukewarm success. Challenges lies in retailer's understanding of customer's needs and motivations and most importantly ,such parameters and perceptible dimensions of the shopping experience which are considered more important by consumers in evaluating a store.(Nagella & Reddy,2018).

People purchase new product which are entering into market, success of that lies in customers' hand. Customer satisfaction is essential to manufacturers as well as retailers to decide about product's quality. So they should be gentle towards customers. (Siddharthan& Krishna, 2016).

It was well documented fact that even a minor increase in customer retention rates would dramatically increase profits in retail. In order to comprehend the consumer preferences related to organized retail stores, the present study provided an understanding of key parameters affecting consumer evaluation of a retail store. It also compared the performance of selected organized retail formats dealing in Food and Grocery on the basis of identified parameters.

This study assisted the concerned authorities to create awareness about what actually customers want from stores varying from their age group, occupation, gender, etc. (Karki, 2018).

This study helped to explain the customer satisfaction regarding customers as they will stay loyal longer, will buy more as the retailer introduces new products and upgrades existing brands, talk favorably about the retailer and its merchandise, pay less attention to competing brands and advertising and is less sensitive to price, offers products/service ideas to the retailer and costs less to serve than new customers.

1.6 Definition of the Concepts and the Variables:

Customer satisfaction: Saxena .(2012). defined customer satisfaction is a function of customer's expectation from firm. It is solely related to customer's viewpoint towards that product.

Price: Pride & Ferrell.(2008). stated that price is the value placed on what is exchanged .Price is the basic factor which influences the customer's satisfaction.

Quality: Quality means those features of products which meet customer needs and thereby provide customer satisfaction. In this sense, the meaning of quality is oriented to income. The purpose of such higher quality is to provide greater customer satisfaction and, one hopes, to increase income. Eldin.(2011).

Location: According to Reilly(19631),Reilly law of retail gravitation which proposes that people are drawn to large shopping thus large cities tend to attract more customers to shop there than smaller ones therefore the need for supermarkets to consider location when put up facilities.

Variety: According to Kotler, product is anything, tangible or intangible, which can be offered to a market for attention, acquisition, use or consumption that might satisfy a need or want.

Service: Vargo& Lusch .(2004). provided a more inclusive definition of service with the derived service perspective, suggesting that all products and physical goods are valued for the inherent service they provide and that the value derived from physical goods is really the service provided by the goods not the good itself.

Loyalty: Customer loyalty means the success of the suppliers to establish long-term relationship with their customers and also achieve rewards in interacting with its customer. It is the tendency to choose a particular product over all others due to satisfaction with the product or service. The customer loyalty always encourages customers to buy more consistently. (Management Study Guide 2008, 43).

1.7 Limitations of the study:

- This study was conducted in order to fulfill partial the requirements for the degree of Bachelor of Business Administration.
- This study was based on limited resource and time.
- Due to lack of time, resource and budget only convenience and random sampling were used.
- There were limited numbers of respondents.
- The sample was not an actual study but rather limited to only to Kathmandu valley

1.8 Report Structure:

This project report work report was done to analyze the Customer Satisfaction towards Bhat-Bhateni Supermarket. The report was arranged into five chapters: chapter I: Introduction, Chapter II: Literature Review, Chapter III: Research method, Chapter IV: Data Presentation and Interpretation and Chapter V: Summary and Conclusions.

Chapter I: Introduction. It included Background Study, Statement of Problem, Objectives, Hypothesis, Research Questions, Significance and Limitations of the Study.

Chapter II: Literature review. It included Theoretical Base, Theoretical Framework, Review of Previous Studies and Research Gap.

Chapter III: Research method. It included Research Approach, Research Design, Types and Sources of Data, Population and Sampling, Data Collection and Methods of Analysis.

Chapter IV: Data Presentation and Interpretation. It included Reliability Analysis, Demographic Profile of Respondents, Descriptive analysis, Correlation Analysis, Regression Analysis and Findings from above analyses.

Chapter V: Summary and Conclusion. It included all the finding that were found in the research and its summary was written as well as conclusion was written.

CHAPTER II: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Base:

This study is based on following theoretical guidelines. They are:

Assimilation theory is based on Festinger's (1957) dissonance theory. Dissonance theory points that consumers make some kind of cognitive comparisons between expectation about product and the perceived product performance.

According to Anderson (1973) customers seek to avoid dissonance by adjusting perceptions about given period to bring it more in line with expectations.

Contrast theory was first introduced by Hovland, Harvey & Sherif (1957). While assimilation theory posits that consumers will seek to minimize the discrepancy between expectation and performance, contrast theory holds that a surprise effect occurs leading to the discrepancy being magnified or exaggerated.

Dewes et al (1972) defined cognitive theory as the tendency to magnify the discrepancy between one's attitudes and attitudes represented by opinion statements.

Negativity theory was developed by Carl Smith & Aronson (1963) suggested that any discrepancy of performance from expectations will disrupt the individual, producing "negative energy".

Accordingly dissatisfaction will occur if perceived performance is less than expectations or if perceived performance exceeds expectations.

Disconfirmation theory argues that satisfaction is related to the size related to disconfirmation experience that occurs as a result of comparing service performance against expectations.

Ekinci et al (2004) cites Oliver's updated definition on disconfirmation theory, which states satisfaction is guest's fulfillment response .it is a judgment that a product or service feature, or a

product or service itself, provided a pleasurable level of consumption related fulfillment, including levels of under-or-over-fulfillment.

Adaption –level theory is consistent with expectation and disconfirmation on satisfaction.

Helson (1964) pointed out that that one perceives stimuli only in relation to an adapted standard. Once created, the ‘adaptation level’ serves to sustain subsequent evaluations in that positive and negative deviations will remain in the general vicinity of one’s original position.

Opponent –Process theory was originally a theory of motivation reformulated by Solomon and Corbit, which has been adapted from the basic physiological phenomena known as homeostasis.

Equity theory was built upon the argument that a “man’s rewards in exchange with others should be proportional to his investments.

Stouffer and his colleagues referred to ‘relative deprivation’ (equity) as the reaction to an imbalance or disparity between what an individual perceives to be the actuality and what he believes should be the case, especially where his own situation is concerned.

2.2 Theoretical Framework: In this study, there are independent as well as dependent variables .A conceptual framework is developed to describe relationship among following variables.

In this theoretical framework, customer satisfaction is dependent variable and price, quality, location, variety, service and loyalty of customer are independent variables.

2.3 Review of Previous studies:

Name of author	Findings
Prasad(2012)	Customers mostly accepted the products and also were satisfied with T24 Sim Card and Pay Back Card.
Thomas(2012)	Behavior, attitude and perceptions towards shopping malls are very much varied.
Prakash &Paramasivam(2013)	Respondents were expecting reduction in price for branded items.
Ubeja(2013)	Females those are dependent or independent are more conscious about sales promotion than males.
Shashikala & Gangatkar .J(2015)	Consumers prefer supermarkets and provisional stores for grocery but are shifted towards supermarkets.
Balagomathi(2016)	Majority of respondents had been visiting one in a month to supermarkets.
Siddharthan& Krishna(2016)	Customers were mostly satisfied with products, appearance of supermarket was average.
Pal(2018)	Variety of products does not have any impact when compared to price and promotion.
Rasoly(2018)	Organized retailers were playing role in urban areas especially in cities.
Karki(2018)	Females were mostly visited being influenced from family and friends

Prasad (2012), A Study on Customer Relationship in Management in Big Bazaar with special reference to Future Value Retail Ltd, Hyderabad. His research objectives were to study about the services provided by Big Bazaar, identify the loyalty programs implemented by Big Bazaar, know about the Customer Service Desk (CSD) services provided by Big Bazaar to Maintain

CRM and know what methods Big Bazaar using to maintain CRM. For this research, 200 respondents were taken. Data were collected through Questionnaires and Random sampling was used. He revealed that respondents were satisfied with Big Bazaar and were attracted mostly due to offer offered. They were aware of T24SIM Card and Pay Back Card and its services were good. Also Staffs listened to complaints to some extent.

Thomas (2012), A Study of Consumer Behavior Approach towards Shopping Mall Attractiveness with special reference to city of Ahmadabad. His research objectives was to focus on the shopping mall attractiveness wherein the attempt was to study the behavior and attitude of the shoppers towards malls thereby bringing out the characteristics of an ideal mall, based on the survey of shoppers in a mega city in the state of Gujarat. 129 respondents were taken. Structured questionnaires were used and exploratory and descriptive were used. He concluded that malls located near residential areas were quite populated. Products offered in the malls were generally perceived to be branded and superior quality which in turn led to generally perception of malls to be expensive. The mall concept was not transparent in the mind of shoppers.

Prakash & Paramasivam (2013), A Study on Customer Satisfaction, Purchase Pattern towards Nilgiri's Supermarket in Coimbatore City. Their objectives for research were to measure the level of customer satisfaction towards Nilgiris supermarket, to assess the purchase pattern of products available in Nilgiri's supermarket, to study the relationship of income level and purchase pattern of consumers and to give suggestions to Nilgiris firm in improving the satisfaction level. Sample size was 60. They explained that most respondents were expecting reduction in price for branded items, responding were expecting adequate space for parking ,availability of baby products was limited in variety.

Ubeja (2013), A Study of Customer Satisfaction of Shopping Malls in Jabalpur City: Comparison between Male and Female. His research objectives were to identify factors of sales promotion schemes on customer satisfaction with reference to shopping malls and to assess the effects of sales promotion schemes on customer satisfaction with respect to gender wise. 200 customers were taken as samples. Structured questionnaires were used and descriptive and empirical designs were used. He revealed that females those were dependent or independent were more conscious about sales promotion which was related to on luck and gift offers in shopping malls. Males were conscious about monetary benefits offers for getting customer satisfaction.

Shashikala & Gangatkar .J (2015), A Study on Comparative Analysis of Consumer Perception towards Supermarkets and Provision Stores in Bangalore. Their research objectives were to

compare and contrast consumer perception towards supermarkets and provision stores. Sample size was 100. Descriptive research design was used and for collection of data interview was done to consumers. They discovered that samples were more educated, young & city bound. Considered quality, price, proximity and hygiene factors the most while purchasing grocery. Also they perceived that provision stores offer more advantages in terms of price, service, quality & home delivery when compared to variety, hygiene, quality and ambience of supermarkets. Consumers prefer both supermarkets and provisional stores to buy groceries and were shifted more towards supermarkets.

Balagomathi (2016), A Study on Consumers Buyer Behaviour in Supermarket in Tirunelveli District. His research objectives were to study the buying pattern of the customers, to study the promotion efforts of the supermarket, to ascertain the level of satisfaction of the customer's towards the supermarkets, to know the problem faced by the supermarket and to make suitable suggestion to facilities better customer satisfaction. Sample size was 120. convenient sampling was used. He observed that it was clear that majority of respondents had been visiting one in a month to supermarkets. No home delivery benefit was available to customers to increase their awareness levels.

Siddharthan & Krishna (2016), A Study on Customer Preference and Satisfaction towards Supermarket with reference towards Palakkad City. Their objectives were to study the personal profile of the respondents, to study the factors influencing the respondents' preferences and satisfaction towards Supermarket in Palakkad district and to offer suggestions relating to the study. 120 respondents were taken as samples. Structured Questionnaire was used. They explained that customers were mostly satisfied with products, appearance of supermarkets was average. Young customers mostly visited. Respondents complained to authority regarding occurrence of any problem. Some were dissatisfied with neatness of supermarket.

Pal (2018), Customers Perception towards Service of Bhat-Bhateni Supermarket in Kathmandu. His objectives were to analyze the factors affecting customers perception, to analyze the relationship between price and customer perception, to analyze the relationship between promotion and customer perception, to analyze the relationship between variety of product and customer perception, to analyze the relationship between service quality and customer perception, to analyze the relationship between location and customer perception and to suggest improve in sales and functions in the BBSM based on results. 70 number of respondents were taken for the research. Descriptive research design was used. Structured and unstructured

questionnaires were used. He revealed that variety of products did not have any impact and price and promotion had positive impact on customer's perception towards service provided.

Rasoly (2018), A Study on Consumer Satisfaction of Supermarket in Mysore City, Mysore. His objectives were to know consumer price satisfaction from supermarket, to know the price differentiation between supermarket and small retail stores, to know the retail trend of supermarkets, then, now and future, to know consumer satisfaction from convenience and environment of supermarket, to know consumer payment system (Cash /Card), to know consumer, prefer about imported products or domestic products and to know foreign and Indian national satisfaction from supermarket. Questions were used for research. 81 respondents were taken as samples. He pointed out that organized retailers were playing a role just in urban areas especially in cities and in some years there would be large number of competitors in the market and current competitors would expand their market share in outlets.

Karki (2018), A Study on Customer Satisfaction on Bhat Bhateni Supermarket (Special reference to Bhatbhateni of Kalanki Branch). Her objectives were to examine reasons for choosing BBSM, to evaluate level of consumer satisfaction on price charged, service delivered and product variety offered by BBSM, to assess variation in customer satisfaction among age group, gender and occupation and to investigate different factors affecting customer satisfaction in BBSM, Kalanki. Descriptive research design was used. Questionnaire was used. 45 respondents were used as samples. She analyzed that female customers mostly visited due to product range followed by accessibility and influence from friends and family. Customers were neutral with price charged and service delivered by supermarkets.

2.4 Research Gap:

After studying previous researches in supermarkets, female customers were conscious about sales promotion, influenced by friends & family so mostly visited one in a month to supermarkets. Quality of service, brand, price, promotion had impact when compared to variety of product.

Loyalty of customer was not taken into consideration. Issues and problems related to customers were not studied.

CHAPTER III: RESEARCH METHOD

3.1 Research Approach:

Customer satisfaction towards Bhat-Bhateni Supermarket used mix research approach. Quality, service and loyalty were variables related to qualitative approach. Price, location and variety were variables related to quantitative approach.

In quantitative approach, mean, standard deviation, correlation, regression, ANOVA were used to analyze the data and to draw conclusion. Also it helped to know how and why things happen in a society.

In qualitative approach, depth knowledge and solutions of issues was found rather than only drawing conclusion. Questionnaire & interview were used to collect data.

3.2 Research Design:

For this research causal comparative research design was used. It showed the cause and effect of dependent variable with independent variables .In order to explain facts and characteristic related to research descriptive research design was used.

Regarding causal comparative research design price, location, quality, service, loyalty, variety which were independent variables were the cause and customer satisfaction which was dependent variable had effect .With the increased in price of product , the customer satisfaction were affected .This showed how causal comparative research design related the variables with each other.

3.3 Types of Data and its Sources:

There are basically two types of data .primary and secondary.

Primary data are the data collected by him /her as per objective of research.

In this study, primary data were used. It was generated through interview (face –to-face, personal), questionnaire (structured).

3.4 Population and Sampling:

In Kathmandu valley, there are 10 supermarkets (Bhat-Bhateni supermarket, Bluebird Department Store, Kasthamandap Bazaar, Family Store, R.B. Complex, Dillibazar supermarket, Gemini Supermarket, Namaste Supermarket, Grihini supermarket, Saleways Department Store.) All supermarkets in Kathmandu valley were taken as population for this research.

Due to limited time, energy & budget samples were taken from Bhat-Bhateni supermarket only. Convenience sampling of non-probability sampling as well as random sampling of probability sampling were taken into consideration for required specific research.

3.5 Instrumentation (Tools and Techniques):

In order to collect needed data, interview and questionnaire were used. Structured, unstructured, descriptive, yes/no, multiple choice questionnaires were used. For interview, face-to-face, personal type was used. Those tools helped to find the tentative result needed for this research study.

In order to examine the validity and reliability of questionnaire, pilot testing was conducted.

In order to examine the validity & reliability of Likert scale questionnaire Cronbach Alpha test was used. Value ranges from 0 to 1.

3.6 Methods of Analysis:

3.6.1 Data Processing Techniques:

Data Processing is the sequence of operations performed to convert raw data into usable form (either automatically or manually). There is mainly three types of data processing methods: manual data, mechanical data & electronic data. Data was edited, coded, classified, tabulated

and summarized in order to analyze the data needed. Tabulation process was mostly used. To summarize the data table, graphs and charts was used to some extent. Bar diagram, pie chart was used mostly for mathematical tools to analyze the collected data to be processed. Most common way to analyze is computer via SPSS, Excel and MS Word.

3.6.2 Data Analysis (Tools and Techniques):

In order to analyze the data, processing was done through mathematical, statistical tools.

Mathematical tools: Under this tool, percentage analysis was used.

Statistical tools: In order to explain nature and characteristic of data, descriptive statistical was used. Under descriptive statistics, following tools was used:

- (i) Mean: This measured the central tendency that offers a general picture of data calculating average of series of data.

$$\bar{x} = (\sum x_i) / n \quad - \text{(Adhikari \& Pandey, 2017)}$$

Where, \bar{x} =mean

x_i = number of independent variables=1,2,3,4,5,6.

n =1, 2,3,4,5,6

- (ii) Standard deviation: In order to find variance between observed data and estimated data this method was used.

$$\sigma = \sqrt{(\sum (x - \bar{x})^2) / n} \quad - \text{(Adhikari \& Pandey, 2017)}$$

Where σ =standard deviation

Under inferential statistics, following tools was used.

- (i) Correlation: In order to find the cause and effect relationship between variables. Multiple correlations was used.

$$r = (N \sum dx dy - \sum dx \sum dy) / (\sqrt{N \sum dx^2 - (\sum dx)^2} \sqrt{N \sum dy^2 - (\sum dy)^2}) \quad - \text{(Bam, 2015)}$$

- (ii) Regression: A statistical technique that will be used to see the degree of relationship between variables. Multiple regressions was used.

$$y = \alpha + \beta_0 + \beta_1 x_1 + \beta_2 x_2 + \dots + \beta_k x_k + e - (\text{Bam, 2015})$$

- (iii) ANOVA (analysis of variance): To study over more than two samples at a time this method was used. Also, this method helped to study the area of variance and degree of variance.

$$F = \text{MSR} / \text{MSE} - (\text{Bam, 2015})$$

$$\text{MSR} = \text{SSR} / k = \Sigma (\hat{y} - \bar{y})^2 / k$$

$$\text{MSE} = \text{SSE} / n - k - 1 = \Sigma (y - \hat{y})^2 / n - k - 1$$

where, k=number of independent variables

Customer satisfaction=f (price, quality, location, service, variety, loyalty)

$$Y = a + b_1 x_1 + b_2 x_2 + b_3 x_3 + b_4 x_4 + b_5 x_5 + b_6 x_6 + e$$

where, x_1 =price of product, x_2 =quality of product, x_3 =location of supermarket, x_4 =service provided by staffs, x_5 =variety of products & x_6 =loyalty of customers.

CHAPTER IV: PRESENTATION and ANALYSIS of DATA

4.1 Reliability Analysis of the Variable Items:

To check the reliability of variables, Cronbach Alpha test was used. Its value ranges from 0 to 1. In overall, the Cronbach alpha test value should be at least 0.6 or more.

Table 4.1 Reliability Statistics of Different variables.

S. N	Variables	C Alpha	No. of Items
1	Price	0.601	3
2	Quality	0.654	3
3	Location	0.615	3
4	Variety	0.591	3
5	Service	0.593	3
6	Loyalty	0.698	3
7	Overall	0.893	18

To analyze the reliability of this study, Cronbach Alpha test was carried out. Above table showed the reliability of different variables. In overall, the data collected was reliable by 89.3%.

4.2 Demographic Profile of Respondents:

The variations that show the frequency distribution of age, gender, level of education, employment status, monthly income and some queries are presented as follows:

Gender of Respondents:

Table 4.2 Gender of Respondents

Gender	Frequency
Male	57
Female	48
Total	105

Figure 4.1 Gender of Respondents.

From above table and chart we got to know degree of respondent male is 54.28 % and that of female is 45.71 %.

Age of Respondents:

Table 4.3 Age of respondents

Age	Frequency	Percent
Below 18	1	0.95
18-25	51	48.57
26-33	39	37.14
More than 34	14	13.33
Total	105	100

Figure 4.2 Age of Respondents

From above table and figure, majority of respondents were of age between 19-25, and minority was of age under 18. 26-33 and above 34 were also the respondents for this research.

Educational Status:

Table 4.4 Educational Status

Level of education	Frequency	Percent
Illiterate	-	-
Below SLC/SEE	1	0.95
+2	2	1.90
Bachelor	69	65.71
Masters	33	31.43
Total	105	100

Figure 4.3 Educational Status of Respondents

In above figure and table, majority of respondents were graduate(65.91%) and minority was of under SLC/SEE(0.95%).

Employment Status:

Table 4.5 Employment Status

Employment Status	Frequency	Percent
Business	10	9.52
Service	42	40
Student	51	48.57
Unemployed	1	0.95
Household	1	0.95
Total	105	100

Figure 4.4 Employment Status of Respondents

From the table and figure, majority of respondents were students(48.57%) and minority were unemployed and of household(0.95%). Some were involved in business and some in service sector.

Monthly Salary:

Table 4.6 Monthly Salary

Monthly salary	Frequency	Percent
Less than 10000	41	39.05
10001-30000	28	26.67
30001-50000	12	11.43
More than 50001	24	22.85
Total	105	100

Figure 4.5 Monthly Income of Respondents

From table and figure ,majority of respondents earned less than 10000(39.05%) and minority was 30001-50000(11.43%).some were earning between 10001-30000 and more than 50001.

Shopping Behaviour:

Table 4.7 Shopping Behaviour

Duration	Frequency	Percent
Less than 6 months	22	20.95
6 months-1 year	22	20.95
1-5 years	38	36.19
5-10 years	15	14.29
More than 10 years	8	7.62
Total	105	100

Figure 4.6 Shopping Behaviour of Respondents

From the table and figure, most were Bhat- Bhateni Supermarket customers for 1-5 years(36.19%). And less respondents were customers for more than 10 years(7.62%). Also less than 6 months, 6 months to 1 year and 5-10 years were there available.

Shopping Areas:

Table 4.8 Shopping Areas

Reason	Frequency	Percent
Grocery	46	43.81
Clothing	42	40
Cosmetics	14	13.33
Furniture	3	2.86
Total	105	100

Figure 4.7 Shopping Areas of respondents

From table and figure, grocery is the majority among the respondents visiting supermarket and furniture is the minority among them.

4.3 Descriptive Analysis:

Descriptive analysis of price:

4.9 Descriptive Statistics of price of products

Statement	N	Mean	Standard deviation
Price is suitable for all income based customers.	105	2.8952	0.84266
Price of products have effect on customer satisfaction	105	2.2286	0.60855
Price is more if compared to other stores	105	2.3143	0.65507
Overall	105	2.4794	0.70209

Price of products were drifted slightly towards neutral option .so it can be concluded that price sometimes affect the customer’s satisfaction and vice versa. And there was only slightly deviation between customer satisfaction and price of products.

Descriptive analysis of quality of products:

Table 4.10 Descriptive Statistics of Quality of products

Statement	N	Mean	Standard deviation
Quality of product is there in this Supermarket	105	2.9429	0.86412
Quality influences the price of products.	105	2.2762	0.71381
Products are up to date.	105	2.3238	0.75314
Overall	105	2.5143	0.77702

Most of the respondents agreed that quality is needed for products and there is only slightly deviation between them.

Descriptive analysis of location of supermarket:

Table 4.11 Descriptive Statistics of location of supermarket

Statement	N	Mean	Standard deviation
This location is convenient to customers.	105	2.9048	0.86072
It is located in busy streets.	105	2.2286	0.63937
VIP or Commercial area is taken as supermarkets location.	105	2.3524	0.75931
Overall	105	2.4953	0.75313

Respondents mostly agreed to relationship between to customer’s satisfaction and location of supermarkets. And there is less deviation between them.

Descriptive analysis of variety of products:

Table 4.12 Descriptive Statistics of Variety of products

Statement	N	Mean	Standard deviation
There is variety of products in this store.	105	2.4	0.86157
Products are either expired or Chinese.	105	2.3048	0.74838
Varieties of product affect the Customer’s satisfaction.	105	1.9429	0.71829
Overall	105	2.2159	0.77608

In average it was found that there is relationship between variety of products and customer’s satisfaction. There is less deviation among them.

Descriptive analysis of service of staffs:

Table 4.13 Descriptive Statistics of Service of Staffs

Statement	N	Mean	Standard deviation
Staffs are responsible, helpful and Knowledgeable	105	2.3905	0.86040
People are satisfied with staffs’ behavior.	105	2.3048	0.74838
Service of staffs affects the satisfaction of customers	105	1.9429	0.71829
Overall	105	2.2127	0.77569

Respondents were mostly satisfied to service of staffs towards customers. And deviation was less.

Descriptive analysis of loyalty of customers:

Table 4.14 Descriptive Statistics of loyalty of Customers

Statement	N	Mean	Standard deviation
No stores are reliable than this Supermarket	105	2.9143	0.85613
People are becoming more attracted towards this supermarket	105	2.3048	0.74838
People preferred this supermarket's Product	105	2.4	0.75447
Overall	105	2.5397	0.78633

Majority of respondents were neither satisfied as well as unsatisfied with relationship between customer's satisfaction and loyalty of customers. Also there was deviation between them.

4.4 Correlation Analysis:

Table 4.15 Correlational Analysis of price of products

Statements		Price is suitable for all income based customers	Pricing of products have effect on customer satisfaction.	Price is more if compared to other stores
Price is suitable for all income based customers	Pearson Correlation			
	Sig.(2-tailed)			
	N	105		
Pricing of products have effect on customer satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	.197*		
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.044		
	N	105	105	
Price is more if compared to other stores	Pearson Correlation	.374**	.493**	
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.00	0.00	
	N	105	105	105

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The Sig(2-tailed) was 0.044 which is less 0.05 and price is positively correlated with only slightly difference.

Table 4.16 Correlational Analysis of Quality of products

Statements		Quality of product is there in this supermarket.	Quality influences the price of products.	Products are up to date.
Quality of product is there in this supermarket	Pearson Correlation			
	Sig.(2-tailed)			
	N	105		
Quality influences the price of products	Pearson Correlation	.260**		
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.007		
	N	105	105	
Products are up to date.	Pearson Correlation	.442**	.476**	
	Sig.(2-tailed)	0.00	0.00	
	N	105	105	105

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The sig(2-tailed) was 0.007 which is less 0.05 and quality is positively correlated with only slightly difference.

Table 4.17 Correlational Analysis of location of supermarket

Statements		This location is convenient to customers.	It is located in busy streets.	VIP or Commercial area is taken as supermarkets location.
This location is convenient to customers	Pearson Correlation			
	Sig.(2-tailed)			
	N	105		
It is located in busy streets	Pearson Correlation	.285**		
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.003		
	N	105	105	
VIP or Commercial area is taken as supermarkets location	Pearson Correlation	.302**	.506**	
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.002	0.00	
	N	105	105	105

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The sig(2-tailed) was 0.0025 which is less 0.05 and location is positively correlated with only slightly difference

Table 4.18 Correlational Analysis of Variety of products

Statements		There is variety of products in this store.	Products are either expired or Chinese.	Varieties of product affect the customer's satisfaction.
There is variety of products in this store.	Pearson Correlation			
	Sig.(2-tailed)			
	N	105		
Products are either expired	Pearson Correlation	.689**		

or Chinese	Sig.(2-tailed)	.000		
	N	105	105	
Varieties of product affect the customer's satisfaction.	Pearson Correlation	.115	.140	
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.243	.154	
	N	105	105	105

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The sig(2-tailed) was 0.1985 which is less 0.05 and variety is positively correlated with slightly difference in significance.

Table 4.19 Correlational Analysis of service of Staffs

Statements		Staffs are responsible, helpful and knowledgeable.	People are satisfied with staffs' behavior.	Service of staffs affects the satisfaction of customers.
Staffs are responsible, helpful and knowledgeable.	Pearson Correlation			
	Sig.(2-tailed)			
	N	105		
People are satisfied with staffs' behavior	Pearson Correlation	.680**		
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.000		
	N	105	105	
staffs affects the satisfaction of customers	Pearson Correlation	.130	.140	
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.187	.154	
	N	105	105	105

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The sig(2-tailed) was 0.1705 which is less 0.05 and service is positively correlated with slightly difference

Table 4.20 Correlational Analysis of loyalty of customers

Statements		No stores are reliable than this supermarket.	People are becoming more attracted towards this supermarket.	People preferred this supermarket's product.
No stores are reliable than this supermarket	Pearson Correlation			
	Sig.(2-tailed)			
	N	105		
People are becoming more attracted towards this supermarket	Pearson Correlation	.276**		
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.004		
	N	105	105	
People preferred this supermarket's product.	Pearson Correlation	.426**	.639**	
	Sig.(2-tailed)	.000	.000	
	N	105	105	105

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The sig(2-tailed) was 0.004 which is less 0.05 and loyalty is positively correlated with only slightly difference

4.5 Hypothesis testing results

H₁: there is significant relationship between customer satisfaction and price of products .P value is found to be 0.044 which is less than 0.05(0.044<0.05), there exist relationship between price of products and customer satisfaction. Therefore H₁ is accepted.

H₂: there is significant relationship between quality of products and customer satisfaction .P value is found to be 0.007 which is less than 0.05(0.007<0.05), there exist relationship between quality of products and customer satisfaction. Therefore H₂ is accepted.

H₃: there is significant relationship between location of supermarket and customer satisfaction. P value is found to be 0.025 which is less than 0.05(0.025<0.05), there exist relationship between location of supermarket and customer satisfaction. Therefore H₃ is accepted.

H₄: there is significant relationship between variety of products and customer satisfaction .P value is found to be 0.1985 which is more than 0.05(0.1985>0.05), there exist no relationship between variety of products and customer satisfaction. Therefore H₄ is not accepted.

H₅: there is significant relationship between service of staff and customer satisfaction .P value is found to be 0.1705 which is more than 0.05(0.1705>0.05), there exist no relationship between variety of products and customer satisfaction. Therefore H₅ is not accepted.

H₆: there is significant relationship between loyalty of customers and customer satisfaction .P value is found to be 0.04 which is less than 0.5(0.004<0.05), there exist relationship between loyalty of customers and customer satisfaction. Therefore H₆ is accepted.

4.6 Regression Analysis:

Table 4.21 Modal Analysis

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.965 ^a	.932	.921	.17133

- a. Predictors: (Constant), People preferred this supermarket's product., Service of staffs affects the satisfaction of customers., There is variety of products in this store., This location is convenient to customers., Quality influences the price of products., People are satisfied with staffs' behavior., Price is more if compared to other stores., People are becoming more attracted towards this supermarket., Quality of product is there in this supermarket. , Products are up to date., Price is suitable for all income based customers., It is located in busy streets., No stores are reliable than this supermarket., VIP or Commercial area is taken as supermarkets location., Staffs are responsible, helpful and knowledgeable.

The value of adjusted R square shows the customer satisfaction towards Bhat-Bhateni Supermarket is affected by 92.1% due to price, quality, location, variety, service and loyalty as a whole. And remaining 7.9% is due to other factors that are being held constant but have

impact on customer satisfaction. Standard error estimate =0.17133 which means average variation of the observed data around regression equation.

Table 4.22 ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	35.902	15	2.393	81.539	.000 ^b
	Residual	2.612	89	.029		
	Total	38.514	104			

a. Dependent Variable: Pricing of products have effect on customer satisfaction.

b. Predictors: (Constant), People preferred this supermarket's product., Service of staffs affects the satisfaction of customers., There is variety of products in this store., This location is convenient to customers., Quality influences the price of products., People are satisfied with staffs' behavior., Price is more if compared to other stores., People are becoming more attracted towards this supermarket., Quality of product is there in this supermarket. , Products are up to date. Price is suitable for all income based customers. It is located in busy streets. No stores are reliable than this supermarket. VIP or Commercial area is taken as supermarkets location. Staffs are responsible, helpful and knowledgeable.

P value =0.05(0<0.05), means multiple regression equation is significant at 10% level of significance.

Table 4.23 Coefficients^a for variables

Model	Unstandardized coefficient		Standardized coefficient Beta	t	Sig,	90.0% confidence interval B	
	B	Std.Error				Lower bound	Upper bound
1 (constant)	.029	.102		.288	.774	-0.140	0.198
Price is suitable for all income based customers	.005	.075	.006	.062	.951	-0.120	.130

Price is more if compared to other stores.	1.280	.114	1.378	11.209	.000	1.090	1.470
Quality of product is there in this supermarket.	.260	.083	.370	3.153	.002	0.123	.398
Quality influences the price of products.	.455	.077	.533	5.937	.000	.327	.582
Products are up to date.	-.179	.070	-.221	-2.544	.013	.295	-.062
This location is convenient to customers	-.260	.091	-.368	-2.869	.005	-.411	-.110
It is located in busy streets	.069	.107	.072	.642	.522	-.109	.247
VIP or Commercial area is taken as supermarkets location	-.683	.107	-.852	-6.363	.000	-.862	-.505
There is variety of products in this store.	-.007	.179	-.010	-.041	.967	-.305	.290
Staffs are responsible, helpful and knowledgeable	-.026	.177	-.036	-.144	.886	-.320	.269
People are	.040	.034	.050	1.201	.233	-.016	.096

satisfied with staffs' behavior							
Service of staffs affects the satisfaction of customers.	.041	.025	.049	1.666	.099	0	.083
No stores are reliable than this supermarket	.007	.091	.010	.078	.938	-.144	.159
People are becoming more attracted towards this supermarket	.391	.098	.464	4.008	.000	.229	.553
People preferred this supermarket's product	-.404	.093	-.500	-4.346	.000	-.558	-.249

a. Dependent Variable: Pricing of products have effect on customer satisfaction.

From this table, value of beta is found for all independent variables. In total variables have positive impact in customer satisfaction .Unstandarized coefficient indicates the regression value.

4.7 Major Findings:

The number of samples taken for research study was 105 respondents. Random sampling was carried out to find customer satisfaction from different dimensions like price, quality, location, variety, service and loyalty. Under demographic profile of respondents i.e. Age, Gender, Educational Status, Employment Status, Monthly income, Shopping Behaviour and Shopping Areas .

- (i) The overall reliability (Cronbach Alpha) of the variable is 0.893 i.e. 89.3% ,questionnaires to measure Customer Satisfaction under this study was reliable and valid.
- (ii) Majority of respondents were of age between 19 and 25 (48.57%), and minority was of age under 18(0.95%).
- (iii) Majority of respondent was male (54.28 %) and minority was that of female (45.71 %).
- (iv) Majority of respondents were graduate (65.91%) and minority was of under SLC/SEE (0.95%).
- (v) Majority of respondents were students (48.57%) and minority were unemployed and of household (0.95%).
- (vi) Majority of respondents earned less than 10000(39.05%) and minority was 30001-50000(11.43%).
- (vii) Most were Bhat- Bhateni Supermarket customers for 1-5 years (36.19%). And fewer respondents were customers for more than 10 years (7.62%).
- (viii) There is positive correlation between variables.
- (ix) The value of adjusted R square shows customer satisfaction was affected by 92.1% due to price, quality, location, variety, service and loyalty.
- (x) The value of R square is found to be 0.932 which is 93.2% of total variation in variables i.e. price of products, quality of products, location of supermarket, variety of products, service of staff and loyalty of customers for customer satisfaction towards Bhat-Bhateni Supermarket.

CHAPTER V: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION

5.1 Summary:

This is the research related to Customer Satisfaction towards Bhat-Bhateni Supermarket. Its variables were price of products, quality of products, location of supermarket, variety of products, service of staff and loyalty of customers. In total, 105 respondents were taken as samples. Random as well as descriptive samplings were used. In descriptive analysis some factors were taken like Gender, Age, Educational Status, Employment Status, Monthly Income, Shopping Behaviour and Shopping Areas.

For questionnaire, Yes /No, multiple choice Questions, 5 point likert scale were used. 18 statements were of likert scale type questions. Data were collected using convenient sampling under non-probability sampling method. For data analysis, SPSS as well as MS-Word was used to check reliability analysis, demographic profile analysis, correlational analysis, hypothesis testing and regression analysis.

In overall Cronbach Alpha was found to be 89.3%. Majority of respondents were of age between 19 and 25 (48.57%), and minority was of age under 18(0.95%).Majority of respondent was male (54.28 %) and minority was that of female (45.71 %).Majority of respondents were graduate (65.91%) and minority was of under SLC/SEE (0.95%).Majority of respondents were students (48.57%) and minority were unemployed and of household (0.95%).Majority of respondents earned less than 10000(39.05%) and minority was 30001-50000(11.43%).Most were Bhat-Bhateni Supermarket customers for 1-5 years (36.19%). And fewer respondents were customers for more than 10 years (7.62%).The value of adjusted R square shows customer satisfaction was affected by 92.1% due to price, quality, location, variety, service and loyalty. The value of R square is found to be 0.932 which is 93.2% of total variation in variables i.e. price of products, quality of products, location of supermarket, variety of products, service of staff and loyalty of customers for customer satisfaction towards Bhat-Bhateni Supermarket.

Regarding Hypothesis testing: P value was found to be 0.044 which was less than 0.05(0.044<0.05), relationship between price of products and customer satisfaction exist.P value

was found to be 0.007 which was less than 0.05($0.007 < 0.05$), relationship between quality of products and customer satisfaction exist. P value was found to be 0.025 which was less than 0.05($0.025 < 0.05$), relationship between location of supermarket and customer satisfaction exist .P value was found to be 0.1985 which was more than 0.05($0.1985 > 0.05$), no relationship between variety of products and customer satisfaction exist .P value was found to be 0.1750 which was more than 0.05($0.1750 > 0.05$), no relationship between service of staffs and customer satisfaction exist. P value was found to be 0.004 which was less than 0.05($0.004 < 0.05$), relationship between loyalty of customers and customer satisfaction exist.

5.2 Conclusions:

This research provides insight about the various dimensions and their association with customer satisfaction .The study has come up with the findings that were requested through research objectives. The relationship of customer satisfaction dimension identified (price, quality, location, variety, service and loyalty) are tested with customer satisfaction. It is clear that analysis and findings helps in testing factors relating to customer satisfaction. It was found that all variables have positive correlation with customer satisfaction.

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